

SOCIO-ECONOMIC GEOGRAPHICAL ASPECTS OF PILGRIMAGE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN TASHKENT REGION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6496687>

Abduhaliqov K.A.¹

*Parkent district of Tashkent region 24th General Secondary School
Tashkent state pedagogical university named after Nizami*

Abstract: *The article describes the scientific and theoretical aspects of pilgrimage tourism and the reforms being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to develop tourism. He also spoke about the opportunities, problems and solutions for the development of pilgrimage tourism in Tashkent region.*

Keywords: *Tourism, pilgrimage tourism, shrine, historical recreation, infrastructure, spiritual and cultural heritage, historical sites, sacred places, industry, ancestors, social spheres, visa Central Asia*

The reforms being carried out in our country are reflected not only in various sectors of the economy - industry, agriculture, transport, tourism, social spheres - health, sports, education. At the same time, a number of good deeds aimed at improving the spiritual environment and cultural life in our country are an example of the high attention paid to our historical values and ancestors. Today, the work of preserving the heritage of our ancestors, bringing their work to the world, and beautifying their places of residence and graves continues. The tombs of saints and clerics, who are famous in the Islamic world, are being turned into shrines, and tourism is being developed in these areas, attracting a large number of tourists.

Increasing the attractiveness of the region for tourism development depends, first of all, on increasing the interest in learning about its historical and cultural potential. It includes historical sites, shrines and other spiritual and cultural monuments, folk crafts, museums. Historical and cultural heritage encompasses the entire socio-cultural environment, along with existing traditions and customs, as well as features of everyday life. Almost all the shrines are of interest to tourists. Today, there are more than 10 major centers of pilgrimage tourism in the world, including the presence of

*Abduhaliqov Kalmakhan Abdumalik oğlu – Parkent district of Tashkent region 24th General Secondary School is a teacher, Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami. kalmamaxan_geo@mail.ru

Central Asian countries, where Islamic values prevail, which testifies to the great potential for the development of this sector in our country.

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev focused on the tourism potential of the country. "Uzbekistan has long been one of the hotbeds of world civilization. It is no secret that many scholars, scientists and great commanders came from this country. It is also the land of the great saints of our country, where such ancestors were born and created, and the fact that we have the honor to live, arouses a sense of pride in our hearts."²

The scientific basis of each science and direction develops and changes depending on the results of practice and scientific progress. In particular, although pilgrimage tourism is a new direction, it has a historically formed scientific basis and needs to be further developed. Historical and cultural monuments, memorial shrines and other spiritual and cultural monuments, folk crafts, museums, which have a rich centuries-old heritage in our country, attract tourists. According to the World Tourism Organization, the first half of the XXI century is called the period of tourism.³ In recent years, more attention from the state to the service sector has led to an increase in the number of tourists from 70 million to 1.235 billion in the last 30-40 years. It is estimated that more than 200 million people visit pilgrimage tourism each year. At present, the country pays more attention to the development of regional tourism. In particular, the adoption of the Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3514 of February 7, 2018 "On measures to ensure the accelerated development of domestic tourism" and the reform of the visa system, including visa-free travel to 45 countries from 2019 The introduction of the system (electronic visa system and types of visas for educational tourism "Studentvisa", "Academicvisa") has paved the way for further development of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan. According to statistics, in 2017, Uzbekistan was visited by 2.7 million tourists, and in 2018 - more than 5.3 million tourists.⁴ In order to further develop this sector, a concept for the development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2025 has been developed. According to this concept, by 2025 the number of foreign tourists will increase by 9-10 m It is planned to increase the number of million people, hold various exhibitions and competitions, turn Uzbekistan into a country of festivals, and

² Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021. PF-4947, February 7, 2017.

³ <https://www.e-unwto.org>. UNWTO Annual report.

⁴ <https://uzbektourism.uz/news/view?id=964>

thus develop event tourism. Adoption of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 16, 2017 "On priority measures for the development of the tourism industry in 2018-2019" is favorable for the rapid development of the industry creating an environment to expand the economic potential and income base of the regions, increase the flow of tourists to our country, as well as the active and comprehensive promotion of national tourism products in the world market.

Pilgrimage in the East means "pilgrimage", "visiting holy places", and pilgrimage includes tourism and religious tourism in the direction of enlightenment. The term pilgrimage tourism is a combination of two words, "pilgrimage" and "tourism." The word tourism in French means tourisme - travel, recreation, as well as sports and general educational or political-educational tasks. The concept of pilgrimage is to travel to religious centers, holy places outside the usual environment for tourists, the interval of which is up to 6 months. Pilgrimage is the practice of visiting holy places, graves and cemeteries to perform certain religious and enlightenment prayers. Objects with the status of sacred places are places where a single event took place from a religious point of view, places where great saints of all times and their companions are buried, sanctuaries of lost religions, objects of perennial shrines are invisible to nature. are the only landscapes created by the forces.

The development of pilgrimage traditions is common to all major religions. In Islam, Mecca and Medina are the main cities of pilgrimage tourism. In addition, Jerusalem (Khalifa Umar Mosque on Mount Moria), Istanbul (Blue Mosque), Damascus (Umayyad Mosque), Baghdad (Golden Mosque), Cairo (Ibn Tulun and Sultan Hasan Mosque) and Delhi (Qutb Minor Tower and Power) ul Islam Mosque) are also important holy shrines for Muslims. In practice, pilgrimage tourism includes all types of tourist services related to religion, various mystics and inexplicable events and traditions. Today, the tourism industry is developing very rapidly, and the geographical problems and opportunities for the development of tourism and recreation in Uzbekistan, such as travel and historical tourism, pilgrimage, ecotourism, educational tourism, sports, medical tourism. The competition in the international tourism market is growing day by day. Covering the mountainous and foothill areas of Tashkent region, the region is distinguished by its richness of natural and historical recreational facilities, the uniqueness of its nature and the formation of infrastructure of national importance. This will further expand the possibilities of organizing and connecting pilgrimage tourism in the district. Today, there are more than 73

shrines in the region, including the presence of Central Asian countries dominated by Islamic values, which testifies to the great potential for the development of this network in our country. In various regions of Uzbekistan, including Tashkent region, there are great opportunities for the development of a number of types of tourism, especially pilgrimage tourism. To increase the attractiveness of the region for the development of tourism in Tashkent region, first of all, to increase interest in learning about its historical and cultural potential. That is, to attract more tourists by providing accurate information about the historical monuments, memorial shrines and other spiritual and cultural monuments, folk crafts, museums in the region. For this purpose, in order to attract tourists to the existing tourist facilities and shrines in Tashkent region, advertisements will be provided, infrastructure must be created. Importantly, we can see that the formation of sacred shrines in areas where rivers, streams, springs, mines, handicrafts, agriculture, livestock, trees, various medicinal plants grow, is associated with various historical and geographical factors. The largest shrines in Tashkent are monuments located in Zangiota district and in the center of Tashkent city. , differs from others by its geographical and historical location. Most of the shrines in Tashkent region are located in Ahangaron, Piskent, Ortachirchik, Bekabad districts, and scholars living in these areas have made a worthy contribution to the development of science and culture. The sacred shrines named after our ancestors are a testament to the way of life, culture, millennia of our people with its religious and religious values as well as its uniqueness in architecture and architecture, it will serve as a great legacy for future generations. The monument is located in Tashkent region in order to preserve the rich spiritual and cultural heritage of our people, to preserve, repair and beautify each step, monument and shrine, to further develop their infrastructure and to create favorable conditions for visitors and tourists. 20 of the shrines and shrines were given to the regional branch of the International Charitable Fund "Golden Heritage" and 6 to the "Foundation". In particular, the regional branch of the International Heritage Fund "Golden Heritage" organized "Paygambar ota" (2001), "Shoabdumalik bobo" (2009-2018) in Ahangaron district, "Zarkent ota" (2002) in Parkent district. "Bukhangar Buva", "Ansoriy Bobo" and "Hazrati Mullo" shrines in Bostanlyk district are currently being designed. Zangiota, Hazrati Ali, Shodimalik ota, Buzruk ota, Zarkent ota, Paygambar ota, Shamirqori avliyo, Parpi ota, Sheikh Umar Vali Buzruk ota, Qirq qiz are famous places in the region. Pilgrims from the republics of Central Asia,

Russia, Kazakhstan, Turkey, Indonesia, Malaysia, Iran and Pakistan are visiting.

REFERENCES:

1. PF-5611 "On additional measures for the accelerated development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan", January 5, 2019.
2. Abduxalikov K.A. Mountain and Mountain Tourism in Uzbekistan: Potential and Development Factors International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2000-005X Vol. 3 Issue - 2019, Pages: 32-35.
3. Report of the Tashkent Regional Branch of the Golden Heritage International Charitable Foundation.